

Research on Improved Two-step Calculation Method Based on P_1 Theory

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the core nuclear design of Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR) primarily employs a two-step approach based on diffusion theory. The diffusion equation is derived from the neutron transport equation by first applying the P_1 approximation to obtain the P_1 equations, followed by the diffusion approximation. Compared to the diffusion equation, the P_1 equations directly retain complete first-order anisotropic scattering, involving fewer approximations. Therefore, this study proposes to replace diffusion theory with P_1 theory, constructing a P_1 homogenization method and a coarse-mesh variational nodal method for solving the P_1 equations, thereby establishing a comprehensive P_1 two-step framework. Validation conducted on a two-dimensional MTR core demonstrates that, compared to the traditional diffusion method, the P_1 method reduces the deviation in the effective multiplication factor by 466 pcm and the maximum deviation in power distribution by 1.5%, while maintaining comparable computational time. These results confirm that the P_1 two-step framework offers distinct advantages over the diffusion-based two-step approach for solving PWR core problems.

Keywords: Anisotropic scattering; P_1 equation; Variational nodal method; Two-step method

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the core nuclear design of Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR) primarily employs a two-step approach based on diffusion theory. The neutron diffusion equation is derived from the neutron transport equation. This derivation first involves the P_1 approximation, where the angular dependence of the flux and scattering cross sections is expanded using first-order spherical harmonics. Subsequently, the diffusion approximation is applied, which considers only isotropic scattering. These approximations lead to insufficient computational accuracy for the diffusion equation when applied to cores with strong anisotropic scattering and high heterogeneity.

To address this issue, some scholars have attempted to reduce the theoretical approximations applied to the neutron diffusion equation. A significant body of research has focused on the simplified SP_3 theory^[1], which primarily aims to improve computational accuracy by increasing the order of the angular expansion of the neutron angular flux density from 1 to 3 and by refining the spatial mesh from the assembly scale (approx. 20 cm) or quarter-assembly scale (approx. 10 cm) down to the pin-cell scale (approx. 1 cm). However, the SP_3 equations are essentially equivalent to two coupled diffusion equations. Coupled with the refined spatial mesh, their computational cost often exceeds that of the two-step method based on diffusion theory by over two orders of magnitude, rendering them impractical for engineering applications. Consequently, Zhuang Kun^[2] from Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics adopted a different approach. They introduced an Eddington factor as a transport correction term into the neutron diffusion equation to describe the neutron angular distribution effect. The resulting equation is termed the Quasi-Diffusion equation. They demonstrated that the computational cost of the Quasi-Diffusion equation is comparable to that of the diffusion equation, while its accuracy is significantly higher in scenarios with strong anisotropic scattering. The derivation of the Quasi-Diffusion equation still relies on the diffusion approximation. Consequently, it cannot account for the coupling between neutron currents of different energy groups. Building upon this, Qin Junwei^[3] from Xi'an Jiaotong University proposed directly utilizing the P_1 equations and solving them using a finite difference method for pin-by-pin neutronics calculations. Their results demonstrated that the accuracy of the P_1 equations is comparable to that of the simplified SP_3 equations, while their computational requirement remains similar to that of the diffusion equation.

Therefore, this paper proposes an alternative solution strategy: replacing the original diffusion equation with the P₁ equations in the conventional two-step calculation scheme. To obtain the cross-section parameters required for solving the P₁ equations and to enable their accurate solution within a coarse-mesh nodal framework, this study derives a homogenization methodology and a variational nodal solution approach^[4] specifically tailored for the P₁ equations. Building upon this foundation, a comprehensive theoretical framework for a two-step P₁ calculation methodology—spanning from assembly-level lattice calculations to full-core computations—has been established and validated through comparative analysis using the MTR core model.

2. Theoretical Model

2.1. Second-order odd-even type P1 equation

In the solution process using the variational nodal method, it is necessary to derive the functional based on second-order equations. Therefore, the first step involves deriving the second-order form from the P₁ equations. The first-order multi-group steady-state neutron P₁ equation defined within the core block is as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{r,g}\psi_g(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v\Sigma_{f,g'}\psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{g' \neq g}^G \Sigma_{s,gg',0}\psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{3} \nabla \psi_g(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{t,g}\mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,gg',1}\mathbf{J}_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2)$$

Where: $\mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{r})$ is neutron current density (cm²·s⁻¹); g is group index; g is location index; $\Sigma_{r,g}$ is removal cross section (cm⁻¹); ψ_g is neutron flux density (cm⁻²·s⁻¹); χ_g is fission spectrum; k_{eff} is core effective multiplication factor; $v\Sigma_{f,g'}$ is neutron production cross-section (cm⁻¹); $\Sigma_{s,gg',0}$ is zero-order scattering cross-section (cm⁻¹); $\Sigma_{t,g}$ is total cross-section (cm⁻¹); $\Sigma_{s,gg',1}$ is first-order scattering cross-section (cm⁻¹).

By modifying the neutron P₁ equation, a second-order even-odd type neutron P₁ equation can be obtained:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}_{gg}\nabla\psi_g(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{r,g}\psi_g(\mathbf{r}) = S_{g,0}(\mathbf{r}) - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{S}_{g,1}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{t,1} - \Sigma_{s,11,1} & \cdots & -\Sigma_{s,1G,1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -\Sigma_{s,G1,1} & \cdots & \Sigma_{t,G} - \Sigma_{s,GG,1} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$S_{g,0}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v\Sigma_{f,g'}\psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{g' \neq g}^G \Sigma_{s,gg',0}\psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{g,1}(\mathbf{r}) = - \sum_{g' \neq g}^G \mathbf{D}_{gg'}\nabla\psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (6)$$

Where: \mathbf{D} is diffusion coefficient matrix; $S_{g,0}$ is zero-order source (cm⁻³·s⁻¹); $\mathbf{S}_{g,1}$ is 1st-order source (cm⁻³·s⁻¹).

Compared to the diffusion equation, the leakage term in the P₁ equations incorporates coupling effects between different energy groups and different directions. This enables the P₁ equations to more accurately account for anisotropic scattering and to better handle problems with steep flux gradients at material interfaces.

2.2. Functional Establishment and Discretization

According to the Galerkin variational principle, which is well-established for neutron transport problems[4], a global functional is established for the steady-state neutron P1 equations over the entire solution domain and its boundaries. The global functional takes the form of a summation of partial functionals defined on individual nodes. The expressions for the global functional and the partial functionals are as follows:

$$F[\psi_g(r), J_g(r)] = \sum_v F_v[\psi_g(r), J_g(r)] \quad (7)$$

$$F_v[\psi_g(r), J_g(r)] = \int [-\nabla\psi_g(r) \cdot \mathbf{D}_{gg}\nabla\psi_g(r) + \Sigma_{r,g}\psi_g(r)^2 - 2\psi_g(r)S_{g,0}(r) - 2\nabla\psi_g(r) \cdot \mathbf{S}_{g,1}(r)] dV + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^6 \int [\mathbf{n}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{J}_g(r)] \psi_g(r) dS \quad (8)$$

Where: v is nodal index; γ is surface index.

It can be demonstrated that the Euler-Lagrange form of the aforementioned functional yields the P1 equations, and that the boundary conditions satisfy both the internal continuity boundary conditions and the full-reflection boundary conditions required by the P1 equations.

Within each nodal volume, the neutron flux, surface net neutron current, and source term are spatially discretized via direct expansion using three-dimensional basis functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_g(r) &\approx \sum_{i=1}^I \varphi_{g,i} f_i(r) = \mathbf{f}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}_g, \quad r \in V_v \\ \mathbf{n}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{J}_g(r) &\approx \sum_{i=1}^I j_{\gamma,g,i} h_{\gamma,i}(r) = \mathbf{h}_\gamma^T \mathbf{j}_{\gamma,g}, \quad r \in S_\gamma \\ S_{g,0}(r) &\approx \sum_{i=1}^I s_{g,i,0} f_i(r) = \mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{s}_{g,0}, \quad r \in V_v \\ \psi_g(r) &\approx \sum_{i=1}^I \varphi_{g,i} f_i(r) = \mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{s}_{g,1}, \quad r \in V_v \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (8) yields the spatially discretized form of the partial functional:

$$F_v[\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g, \mathbf{j}_{\gamma,g}] = \boldsymbol{\varphi}_g^T \mathbf{A}_g \boldsymbol{\varphi}_g - 2\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g^T \mathbf{s}_{g,0} - 2\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g^T \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{g,1} + 2\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{j}_g \quad (10)$$

Where: \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{M} is response matrix; $A_{g,ii'} = \sum_{l=x,y,z} D_{gg}^l P_{ii'}^{ll} + \Sigma_{r,g} V_v \delta_{ii'}$; $P_{ii'}^{ll} = \int \nabla_l f_i \nabla_l f_{i'} dV$; $M_{\gamma,ij} = \int f_i h_{\gamma,i} dS$; $T_{ii'}^l = \int f_{i'} \nabla_l f_i dV$.

In Eq. (10), setting its first variation with respect to the spatial expansion moments of the neutron flux and the surface net neutron current to zero respectively, we obtain:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g = \mathbf{A}_g^{-1} \mathbf{s}_{g,0} + \mathbf{A}_g^{-1} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{g,1} + \mathbf{A}_g^{-1} \mathbf{M} \mathbf{j}_g \quad (11)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\gamma,g} = \mathbf{M}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}_g \quad (12)$$

Where: $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\gamma,g}$ is surface neutron flux.

Therefore, we can define the partial surface neutron current as follows:

$$\mathbf{j}_{\gamma,g}^\pm = \frac{1}{4} \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\gamma,g} \pm \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{j}_{\gamma,g} \quad (13)$$

By simultaneously solving Eq. (12), Eq. (11) and Eq. (13), the discretized steady-state neutron P1 equations can be obtained:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_g = \mathbf{A}_g^{-1}(\mathbf{s}_{g,0} + \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{g,1}) + 2\mathbf{C}_g(\mathbf{j}_g^+ - \mathbf{j}_g^-) \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{j}_g^+ = \mathbf{B}_g(\mathbf{s}_{g,0} + \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{g,1}) + \mathbf{R}_g \mathbf{j}_g^- \quad (15)$$

Where: $\mathbf{C}_g = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{A}_g^{-1}\mathbf{M}$; $\mathbf{R}_g = [\mathbf{M}^T\mathbf{C}_g + \mathbf{I}]^{-1}[\mathbf{M}^T\mathbf{C}_g - \mathbf{I}]$; $\mathbf{B}_g = [\mathbf{M}^T\mathbf{C}_g + \mathbf{I}]^{-1}\mathbf{C}_g^T$.

Eq. (14) and (15) represent the discretized P₁ equations, which can be directly used for numerical solution.

2.3. Homogenization Method for P₁ Equation

The Super-homogenization (SPH) and the Generalized Equivalent Theory (GET)^[5] are the two main methods that meet the requirements of the homogenization theory. Both of which can account for the effects of leakage. In this paper, we have chosen to employ the GET to perform P₁ homogenization.

During the homogenization, the following quantities should be conserved:

- 1) The effective multiplication coefficient:
- 2) The scalar reaction rates in each homogenization region:
- 3) The scalar neutron leakage rate on each surface in the x/y/z directions:

It can be observed that if two of the aforementioned three conservation conditions are satisfied, the third conservation condition will automatically hold. The homogenized constants that satisfy these three conservation conditions are typically referred to as equivalent homogenized constants. A closer examination of these three conservation relations reveals the difficulties inherent in calculating the equivalent homogenized constants. To compute these constants, the exact solution of the heterogeneous reactor must be known in advance, which is unattainable within the normal computational workflow. Furthermore, the solution of the homogenized reactor must also be known, and this homogenized solution is tightly coupled with the homogenized constants, resulting in the problem of solving for equivalent homogenized constants becoming a nonlinear iterative problem. In practical applications, to overcome this difficulty, it is generally necessary to relax certain constraints or increase the number of degrees of freedom to approximate the equivalent homogenized constants. Therefore, based on the GET, the homogenization method for the P₁ equations is presented

By relaxing the constraint of continuous neutron flux density on nodal surfaces, the conservation of reaction rates and neutron leakage rates is achieved, and discontinuity factors are introduced to ensure the conservation of surface flux. The definitions of the homogenized few-group cross-sections and the discontinuity factors (DF) are as follows:

$$\Sigma_{x,g}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\sum_{h \in g} \int \Sigma_{x,h}^{\text{het}}(r) \phi_h^A(r) dV}{\sum_{h \in g} \int \phi_h^A(r) dV} \quad x = a, f, s0, t1, \dots \quad (16)$$

$$\Sigma_{y,g}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\sum_{h \in g} \int \Sigma_{y,h}^{\text{het}}(r) \Omega_u \phi_h^A(r, \Omega) dV}{\sum_{h \in g} \int \Omega_u \phi_h^A(r, \Omega) dV} \quad y = t1, s1 \quad (17)$$

$$f_{u,g}^{\pm} = \frac{\sum_{h \in g} \int \phi_{u,h}^{\pm,A}(r) dS}{\sum_{h \in g} \int \bar{\phi}_{u,h}^{\pm,A}(r) dS} \quad y = t1, s1 \quad (18)$$

Where: hom is results after homogenization; het is results before homogenization; A is results computed under the total reflection boundary condition; Ω is neutron flight angle; $f_{u,g}^{\pm}$ is discontinuity factor; $\bar{\phi}_{u,h}^{\pm,A}$ is the average value of the neutron flux on the assembly surface calculated by the core solution method after homogenization.

It should be noted that for the diffusion coefficient matrix calculation, one must first perform a condensation calculation to obtain the first-order scattering and total cross-sections on the fine-group structure for different angles. Subsequently, the fine-group diffusion coefficient matrix is derived using Eq. (4), followed by condensation to the few group structure.

For a single-assembly calculation with reflective boundaries, the homogenized region is uniform, leading to a flat flux distribution from the core solver. Thus, the $\bar{\phi}_{u,h}^{\pm,A}$ equals the average assembly flux. Therefore the Eq. (18) can be easily calculated.

However, for reflector assemblies or color-set problems, $\bar{\phi}_{u,h}^{\pm,A}$ depends on the results from the core solver. At this stage, it is assumed that only the zeroth-order spatial expansion is employed for the current in the core calculation. Therefore the the zeroth-order expansion moment of the net current on the node surface is equal to the net neutron current in surface γ , which is preserved during homogenization. Based on the variational nodal method, the $\bar{\phi}_{u,h}^{\pm,A}$ can be calculated by Eqs. (14) and (12). Then the DFs for each energy group on surface γ can be given.

3. Verification

This section presents calculations for MTR core problem. To facilitate this analysis, two distinct calculation schemes are defined as follows:

- 1) The nodal P_1 two-step (P_3 - P_1) method involves generating homogenized few-group cross-sections via P_3 MOC heterogeneous transport calculations on single-assembly and one-dimensional reflector models using Bamboo-Lattice^[6]. These cross-sections are then utilized in a core-wide calculation solving the P_1 equation.
- 2) The diffusion two-step (Inflow-Diff) method involves generating homogenized few-group cross-sections via P_0 MOC calculation with "Inflow" transport correction on single-assembly and one-dimensional reflector models. These cross-sections are then utilized in a core-wide calculation solving the standard diffusion equation.

For this problem, the lattice calculations employ a 69-group energy structure. Homogenization and subsequent core calculations utilize a 4-group structure, with energy boundaries set at 10 MeV and 0.78 eV. For the variational nodal solver, the intra-nodal flux expansion is set to 5th order, and the surface net current expansion is set to 0th order. Computational settings, such as maximum iteration counts and convergence criteria, are maintained consistently across all cases, and no acceleration techniques are employed.

The Low Enrichment Uranium (LEU, 20%) loading scheme was selected to verification. The reflector geometry was simplified by replacing part of the graphite reflector with light water. Relevant geometric and material data are provided in *Table 1*. The schematic diagram of the core layout is shown in *Figure 1*, which also presents the three fuel and reflector homogenization calculation models, respectively. It should be noted that for the fuel assemblies, the pure fuel assembly is homogenized using a single-assembly calculation. However, for the control fuel assembly, due to the control blades being located on the outer side of the assembly, a single-assembly calculation with full reflective boundary conditions would lead to insufficient accuracy in its homogenized parameters. Therefore, it is necessary to calculate it together with half of the adjacent fuel assembly on each side. The same approach applies to the flux trap.

Table 1. MTR core material nuclide

Material	Nuclide	Density/ 10^{24}cm^{-3}
Fuel	U-235	2.2536×10^{-3}
	U-238	8.9005×10^{-3}
	Al-27	3.8171×10^{-2}
Clad	Al-27	6.0260×10^{-2}
Control plate	Ag-109	2.3523×10^{-2}
	Cd-113	3.3257×10^{-4}
	In-115	7.6504×10^{-3}
Water	H-1	6.6856×10^{-2}
	O-16	3.3428×10^{-2}

Due to the symmetry of this two-dimensional model, one-quarter of the core was selected for the calculation. The reference solution was chosen as the result from the one-step calculation code Bamboo-Lattice^[6]. Calculations were also performed using both the P₁ two-step method and the diffusion two-step method. The calculation results for the effective multiplication factor are presented in *Table 2*, and the results for the fission rate distribution are shown in *Figure 2*.

Table 2. Results of the effective multiplication factor calculation

	Reference	P ₁	Diffusion	Bias_P ₁ /pcm	Bias_dif/pcm
k_{eff}	1.25041	1.25395	1.25891	354	850
Time/s		0.016	0.016		

Figure 1. MTR core layout diagram

Figure 2. Power Distribution in 1/4 Core: Reference and Deviation

As can be seen from the figure, in the two-dimensional MTR calculation, using the P₁ two-step method reduces the computational error of the effective multiplication factor from 850 pcm to 354 pcm compared to the diffusion two-step method. The nodal power distribution deviation is improved from a range of -3.13% to 2.68% to a range of -2.05% to 2.38%. The root mean square of nodal power

distribution deviation is reduced from 1.45% to 0.96%. These results demonstrate the superiority of the P_1 two-step method over the diffusion two-step method.

4. CONCLUSIONS

To further improve computational accuracy within the two-step framework, this study adopts the P_1 method to replace the original diffusion method. It derives the homogenization methodology and nodal computation method for the P_1 equations. Validation conducted on a two-dimensional MTR core problem demonstrates that the computational accuracy of the P_1 two-step method is significantly higher than that of the diffusion two-step method for this specific problem.

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